

Commonalities and differences between differential object marking and indexing

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1 Introduction

1.1 DOM and DOI

For the purpose of this paper, we define DOM and DOI in the following way. Differential argument coding is a mechanism whereby an argument role may be coded in different ways, depending on factors other than the role itself. When the locus of coding is the argument itself, we speak of differential argument marking. When the locus is anywhere else – in particular, when it is the verb – we speak of differential argument indexing. The role that is the base for DOM and DOI is P.¹

It should be noted that DOM and DOI may co-occur in a single language. Where DOM and DOI are at least to some degree independent, we will look at them separately. However, we will ignore cases where DOM and DOI cooccur under exactly the same conditions because such cases make it impossible to separate the functions of the two. One such case, for instance, are typical antipassives, where the marking of the object changes together with the verbal indexing.

Further, we ignore equipollent DOM systems (i.e. systems where two overt object cases alternate) such as the well-known Finnic ACC/PART alternation. While these should be included in a truly comprehensive account, cursory inspection indicates that they are rather different in functional terms from the more common privative systems (where an overt case alternates with zero marking), so including them would not serve our aim of contrasting DOI and what we consider to be typical DOM.

1.2 Variables and hierarchies

DOM and DOI have received increasing attention in the functional-typological literature of the last three decades (Comrie 1979; Bossong 1985; Croft 1988; Lazard 2001; Aissen 2003; Iemmolo 2011; among others). As a general tendency, DOM (coined by Bossong 1982, 1985) has been in the focus of interest of many researchers, whereas DOI has often been ignored or has been treated as functioning parallel to DOM.

While a multitude of formal and functional variables are known to play a role for DOM and DOI (see Section 3 below for an overview), most of them can be

¹ Note that this is a practical restriction. The notion of object cannot only refer to P, but also to T and G, and differential argument coding is not necessarily restricted to a single role but can also apply to sets of roles, e.g. P/T (direct object) or P/G (primary object). The reason why we ignore T and G as well as other non-core roles is that these have not been intensively discussed in the literature.

The role system used in this paper is based on Dowty (1991), Primus (1999), and Bickel and Nichols (2009). Accordingly, P is defined as the less agent-like argument of a transitive verb.

conveniently classified into two big clusters named “inhérence” and “référence” by Bossong (1998) and roughly corresponding to animacy and identifiability. The values of these variables are often represented in the form of hierarchies so that “higher” referents are more likely to be marked or indexed than “lower” referents. For instance, consider the two hierarchies proposed by Aissen (2003:437):

ANIMACY SCALE: human > animate > inanimate

DEFINITENESS SCALE: personal pronoun > proper name > definite > specific > non-specific

These hierarchies are in turn sometimes integrated into a single hierarchy (Croft 2003:132). This hierarchy is known under various names such as “animacy hierarchy” or “referential hierarchy”.²

EXTENDED ANIMACY SCALE: first/second person pronoun > third person pronoun > proper names > human common noun > non-human animate common noun > inanimate common noun

Applied to DOM and DOI, this hierarchy should predict that P ranking higher are more likely to receive overt marking (Silverstein 1976; Comrie 1989; among others). By contrast, P ranking lower on the hierarchy are predicted to remain unmarked. Thus, for instance, first and second pronouns should be more likely to be case-marked or indexed than third person pronouns.

1.3 Explanations for DOM

Thus far, we have discussed the main parameters that determine DOM and DOI systems. In this section we will summarise the previous explanations that have been proposed for DOM, namely the “distinguishing” and the “indexing” or “highlighting” explanations. Generally, such explanations have been, implicitly or explicitly, also applied to DOI (see Iemmolo 2011). Under one type of analysis, referred to as “distinguishing” here and represented e.g. by Bossong (1985), Comrie (1989), Bossong (1998), Aissen (2003), which covers only case marking, DOM serves to correctly assess the roles of A and P when both A and P share the same semantic properties, like animacy or definiteness. For instance, an animate P would be likely to be interpreted as A if other clues, such as word order, are not available. Case marking on animate Ps is therefore used to prevent such an interpretation.

Under the “indexing” or “highlighting” view (represented e.g. by Hopper and Thompson 1980; Næss 2004, 2007), DOM and DOI serve to highlight salient semantic and pragmatic properties of the referents of arguments, such as animacy, definiteness, or the degree of affectedness (see Siewierska and Bakker 2009:291; Song 2001:156). Marked objects are viewed as prototypical in this approach and are marked in order to emphasise their role for the transitivity of the clause they appear in or simply to draw attention to them.

² Note that Bickel, Witzlack-Makarevich & Zakharko (2014) have shown that there is no statistical support for such a unified hierarchy in the languages of the world. It should therefore be taken as a theoretical construct.

In a similar vein, Nikolaeva (2001) has proposed an information structure based approach to DOM and DOI, according to which these constructions are the grammatical expression of the role of secondary topic (see Dalrymple and Nikolaeva 2011 for definitions and further discussion). In their approach, DOM and DOI are “indexing” strategies, as they are exploited as a means of highlighting the similarities between topical As (which are primary topics) and topical Ps (which are secondary topics), which both tend to be topical – although to a different degree – and overtly coded (Dalrymple and Nikolaeva 2011:15-16). Languages are thus claimed to have the tendency to overtly code topics independently of role and either via indexation or case marking.

In the following section we will present our own data and evaluate the accounts sketched above against our results from the corpus studies of Nepali and Chintang as well as from data based on a cross-linguistic sample.

2 DOM and DOI in Nepali and Chintang

Nepali (Indo-European > Indo-Aryan) and Chintang (Tibeto-Burman > Kiranti) are spoken in Nepal. Their typological profiles are to a large degree compatible with the family branches they belong to (see e.g. Cardona and Jain 2003 for Indo-Aryan and Ebert 2003 for Kiranti). They are good candidates for taking a deeper look at differences between DOM and DOI because each of them has an isolated system (DOM in Nepali, DOI in Chintang) that does not interact with the other differential marking pattern in the pair and because large, annotated corpora are available for both.

The description of DOM and DOI in the following paragraphs is based on fieldwork and corpus research carried out by Robert Schikowski between 2009 and 2012. The relevant corpora are the Nepali National Corpus (NNC) and the Chintang Language Corpus (CLC). A more detailed account is found in Schikowski (2013).

2.1 DOM in Nepali

2.1.1 A quick glance

Nepali uses a large set of postpositions to mark case relations, and many roles take part in differential marking patterns. This is also true of P, which in most verb classes can be either zero-marked as in (1a) or marked by the postposition *-lai* as in (1b). *-lai* will be referred to here as dative because it is also regularly used to mark recipients. The zero-marked case will be called nominative.

(1) Nepali (Indo-Aryan)

- a. *Raches-haru-le bhat kha-e.*
ogre-PL-ERG rice eat-PST.3p
'The ogres had rice.'
(elicitation NP 2012)
- b. *Raches-haru-le manche-lai kha-e.*
ogre-PL-ERG person-DAT eat-PST.3p
'The ogres ate somebody.'

(elicitation NP 2012)

Besides P, DOM in Nepali also affects the roles T and G. However, we will focus on P for several reasons. First, differential marking of T and G has not been extensively described in the DOM literature. Second, P in Nepali is the role that is most frequently eligible for DOM: in a subcorpus of the NNC that was annotated for syntactic and referential variables in Schikowski (2013), 2645 out of 3183 annotated objects³ (83%) have the role P. Last, DOM on T and G is more heavily constrained by verb class than for P, where DOM is possible for all members of the large monotransitive class. Formally, DOM in this class is closely linked to differential agent marking (A-NOM/ERG, see Abadie 1974; Foster 1985; Li 2007b): every bivalent verb whose A can be marked by the nominative or ergative has a P that can be marked by the nominative or dative, and vice versa.

2.1.2 Functional characteristics

Previous linguistic works on DOM in Nepali agree on the fact that DOM is conditioned by animacy and definiteness or specificity (Korolev 1965; Abadie 1974; Li 2007a). Coursebooks usually reduce DOM to animacy, variously drawing the line between humans and non-humans (Gupta and Karmacharya 1981; Mathews 1984) or between animates and inanimates (Sommer 1993; Acharya 1991), while older grammars and grammars written in Nepali tend to ignore the phenomenon altogether (Turnbull 1923; Clark 1963; Khaḍkā 2055 V.S. [= 1998/1999]; Lamsāla 2062 V.S. [= 2005/2006]).

A closer look reveals that while previous accounts do capture a significant portion of the nature of DOM in Nepali, they fail to realise the complexity of this phenomenon. Within the limits of space given here, we will try to show that there are (a) many more factors than just animacy and definiteness/specificity and that (b) the interaction between all factors, including the ones already mentioned, cannot be captured by a rule system.

The most important factor in Nepali DOM is humanness. In the subcorpus of the NNC that was annotated in Schikowski (2013), 68% of all human objects are marked by the dative and 93% of all non-human objects (including animals) are marked by the nominative. Note that the Nepali data only support a binary distinction between humans and non-humans but no complex animacy hierarchy. Specificity cannot compete with this, although it does have a clear effect: whereas only 12% of all objects get the dative on average, 19% of all specific referents get the dative and 97% of all non-specific referents get the nominative. This effect is highly significant ($p < 0.01$ on a Fisher's exact test) and again rather binary than truly hierarchical.

Despite the usefulness of humanness and specificity, they can not explain all P cases. Both non-human and/or non-specific P can be marked by the dative, as shown in (2) and (3), respectively.

(2) Nepali (Indo-Aryan)

Carkune *ḍhunga-lai* *latti-le* *tin* *baji* *han-in*.
rectangular stone-DAT kick-ERG three time hit-PST.3fMH

³ The term "object" in the description of Nepali in this paper refers to all P, T, and G which are eligible for DOM. NPs with case marking fixed on the base of valency classes (e.g. T-NOM, G-DAT) are excluded.

‘She kicked at the rectangular stone three times.’
(NNC:book-fiction-bircharitra-2060.193)

- (3) Nepali (Indo-Aryan)
Gai-lai mar-na pa-ĩ-dain-a, dharmik
 cow-DAT kill-INF get-PASS-NEG.NPST-3s religious
sotāntrata cah-ĩ-dain-a!
 freedom need-PASS-NEG.NPST-3s
 ‘Killing cows is unacceptable, we don’t need religious freedom!’
 (field notes 2011)

On the other hand, both human and specific Ps can be marked by the nominative, as shown in (4) and (5):

- (4) Nepali (Indo-Aryan)
Dosro bissoyuddha-le pāc karodmanche mar-y-o.
 second world.war-ERG five ten.million person kill-PST-3s
 ‘The Second World War killed 50 million people.’
 (NNC:himalkhabarpatrika-2059-02-16.2065)

- (5) Nepali (Indo-Aryan)
Un-le abā phalam-ko dāḥḍa, khukuri ra kei
 3MH-ERG now iron-GEN rod knife and some
ḍhūḅga pāni ochyan-muni luka-erā rakh-ek-i
 stone also bed-under hide-CVB put-PST.PTCP-F
ch-an.
 be.there-3MH
 ‘She hid the iron rod, the knife and also some stones under the bed.’
 (NNC:s02.91)

Example (3) also shows that it is not the case that animate referents marked by the dative must be definite, as claimed by Abadie (1974). Example (2) shows that the dative is not only found on animate specific referents, as claimed by Li (2007a). What holds at least as a very strong tendency, though, is that P referents that are human and specific are almost always marked by the dative. However, counter-examples can be found even for this:

- (6) Nepali (Indo-Aryan)
Mā tim-r-i ama bheṭ-na a-eko.
 1s 2s-GEN-F Mother meet-INF come-PST.PTCP
 ‘I’ve come to meet your mother.’
 (NNC:book-fiction-alikhit-2058.635)

Nevertheless, it may be said that most variation is found within referents that are not at the same time human and specific (“hybrid”). A unified hierarchy of the form human specific > hybrid > non-human non-specific is thus theoretically doubtful but descriptively useful. Hybrid cases are also important because they have high token frequencies: in the NNC subcorpus under discussion there are 1710 non-human specific objects and 73 human non-specific objects, summing up to 56% of all

annotated objects (vs. 1195 non-human non-specific and 205 human specific objects). We will now look at which factors can trigger the dative within the hybrid segment.

One important factor is a certain kind of topicality which may be defined as mental presence: the more a speaker has been thinking about a referent, the more highly topical it is, and the more likely it is to get the dative. A good indicator of this kind of topicality is discourse frequency because mentioning a referent overtly implies activating a mental representation of it. For instance, the example in (7) comes from a short story by Paraśu Pradhāna called “That telegram on the table” (Pradhāna 1997). Beside the protagonist of the story, who is mentioned 94 times, the most frequent referent is a certain telegram (23 mentions), which the protagonist has been pondering about and whose content is only revealed in the end. The high topicality of the telegram is reflected by its being marked by the dative whenever it stands in object position. (7) is the very first sentence of the story.

- (7) Nepali (Indo-Aryan)
Ṭebal-mathi-ko tes akaswaṇi-lai pheri paḍ-y-o.
 table-on-GEN MED.OBL telegram-DAT again read-PST-3s
 ‘Again he read that telegram on the table.’
 (Pradhāna 1997:75)

The same story also illustrates that discourse frequency is only an approximation of mental presence. (8) shows the only instance of the telegram in P where it is marked by the nominative. This sentence refers to an earlier time, when the protagonist did not know yet that the telegram contains the message of his wife’s death and where accordingly he had not yet been thinking as much about it. The telegram is represented by the demonstrative *tyo*:

- (8) Nepali (Indo-Aryan)
Tyo pa-erḷ saed, u khusi ch-ḷ.
 MED get-CVB probably DIST happy be.there-NPST-3s
 ‘Having received it he is probably happy.’
 (Pradhāna 1997:76)

A factor that has featured prominently in many theoretical accounts of DOM (especially in the “distinguishing” type of approach) is disambiguation between A and P. Presently it is not clear to what degree this factor plays a role in Nepali because it is hard to separate from correlating factors. For instance, consider the following example:

- (9) Nepali (Indo-Aryan)
- a. *Tyo ṭhulo kukur tel(-lai) her-dḷi ch-ḷ.*
 MED big dog MED-DAT watch-PROG be.there-NPST-3s
 ‘That big dog is watching it (the cat).’
 (elicitation NP 2012)
- b. *Tel*(-lai) tyo ṭhulo kukur her-dḷi ch-ḷ.*
 MED-DAT MED big dog watch-PROG be.there.NPST-3s
 ‘That big dog is watching it (the cat).’
 (elicitation NP 2012)

This can be interpreted as follows. Both the dog (*kukur*) and the cat (*tyo/tel-*) are equally natural agents of watching. Thus, the only hint to the role distribution is word order. The default monotransitive word order in Nepali is APV. If this order is kept as in (9a), both the nominative and dative are possible on P. However, if P is fronted as in (9b), word order cannot be used any longer as an indicator of role and case must take over – the dative becomes obligatory. The example is additionally motivated by topicality: the fronting in (9b) implies that the cat has been a discourse topic for a longer time (thus, a more faithful English translation would use the passive: ‘It (the cat) is being watched by that big dog.’).

Ambiguity also backs up the central factor of animacy: highly animate Ps are potentially easier to confuse with A and must therefore be marked. Note, however, that highly animate Ps even tend to get the dative when such confusion is extremely unlikely. This is illustrated by (10), where both the semantics of the verb *marnu* ‘kill’ and the ergative marker *-le* make the role distribution very clear but P is nevertheless marked:

(10) Nepali (Indo-Aryan)

Biralo-le musa-lai khela-i khela-i mar-e-jhāĩ,
 cat-ERG mouse-DAT play-CVB play-CVB kill-NMLZ-EQU

manche-le pāni aphu-bhānda nirdha-lai sidhāi
 person-ERG also REFL-COMP weak-DAT directly

mar-i-hal-dāin-a.

kill-LNK-COMPL-NPST.NEG-3s

‘Just like cats kill mice after playing a while with them, people also don’t kill those weaker than them directly.’

(NNC:freeneal-fiction-2061-12-11.261)

The relatively weak impact of ambiguity as compared to other factors is also reflected by quantitative data. The effect of inversion of A and P as in (9) is easiest to observe in elicitation. In the annotated subcorpus of the NNC, inversion is also relevant (i.e. it produces a statistically significant effect on DOM as judged by a χ^2 test) when looked at in isolation but falls out under fast backwards elimination when all factors are put together in a logistic regression model. See Schikowski (2013) for more details.

DOM can also be influenced by affectedness. While there are a few cases where strong affectedness (especially destruction) can make the dative possible in combination with other factors (cf. Schikowski 2013:170), the most direct interaction between these factor and DOM takes place at the other end of the spectrum – effectuated Ps (Ps created through an action) can only ever be marked by the nominative:

(11) Nepali (Indo-Aryan)

Bātti(-lai) kat-y-o.*

light-DAT light-PST-3s

‘He lit a light.’

(Adhikārī 2052 V.S. [= 1995/1996]:77)

More factors are discussed in Schikowski (2013), who also undertakes a more detailed quantitative analysis of the individual factors and uses logistic regression modelling and mixed-effects modelling to combine their effects.

When looking for a common denominator for the factors behind Nepali DOM, the most promising candidate seems to be the discourse-based expectedness of certain referential properties in combination with the role of P. The dative generally correlates with unexpected properties.

For instance, in the already mentioned annotated subcorpus of the NNC only 9% of all Ps are human. Thus, a speaker who has statistical knowledge about the codistribution of roles and animacy should by default not expect a P referent to be human. Similarly, 75% of all Ps in the annotated subcorpus are discourse-new, so a given referent in P is unexpected. Ambiguity effects can also be linked to unexpectedness because they involve Ps in unusual places (preceding A or far away from the predicate).

However, not even unexpectedness can cover all the individual factors that are relevant for DOM. One highly prominent factor that does not fit into the picture is specificity, which favors DOM but at the same time is more common (and thus expected) than non-specificity: about 60% of all Ps in the annotated NNC subcorpus are specific. Thus, it must be concluded that DOM in Nepali is a polyfunctional phenomenon.

To summarise, a great many functional factors have been found to be relevant to DOM in Nepali, and there does not seem to exist a rule system that can model their interplay. There also is no one factor that can bring them all together, although unexpectedness comes at least close to this and many of the relevant factors correlate in addition with topicality or topicworthiness. The most important factors favouring the dative are summarised in Table 1.

Variable	value most strongly associated with DAT	expected on P?
animacy	human	no
specificity	specific	yes
discourse frequency	most frequent referent	no
word order	P fronting	no
unexpectedness	unexpected	no

Table 1: Most important variables and values influencing DOM in Nepali

2.2 DOI in Chintang

2.2.1 A quick glance

Chintang is – as all Kiranti languages – double-marking. Arguments are thus marked by case (ergative on A, nominative [= zero] on S and P), but they are also indexed on the verb, where two distinct patterns exist: one, called S agreement here, is by default associated with S; the other, called A+P agreement here, most frequently indexes two arguments of a transitive predicate, A and an additional argument that is most frequently P but may also be T or G, depending on verb class. Agreement is illustrated below, where (12a) shows a typical intransitive verb and (12b) shows a typical monotransitive verb.

(12) Chintang (Kiranti, Tibeto-Burman)

- a. *Paĩ na ani ba=go-be yu-i-ki.*
 today CTOP 1pi PROX=NMLZ-LOC stay-1piS-IND.NPST
 ‘As for today, we stay in this place.’
 (CLC:ctn_song_RM01.0007)
- b. *Tara esari ani-ŋa them kha-u-ku-m?*
 but right.now 1pi-ERG what see-3[s]P-IND.NPST-1p[i]A
 ‘But what do we see right now?’
 (CLC:LH_Lal.0078)

The argument controlling P agreement must always be in the nominative (i.e. zero-marked as *them* in [12b]). While transitive clauses look most frequently as in (12b), P agreement can also be cancelled, so Chintang has DOI. A agreement cannot occur isolated, so it is changed to S agreement in this case. As a further consequence, the A NP can no longer be marked by the ergative but appears in the nominative. (13) shows two parallel examples where the first displays the normal transitive pattern but the second lacks P agreement. (13b), the examples with no P agreement, is formally very similar to an intransitive clause, but the P NP remains a core argument and is still marked by the nominative.

(13) Chintang (Kiranti, Tibeto-Burman)

- a. *Debi-ŋa seu kond-o-ko.*
 Debi-ERG apple look.for-3[s]P-IND.NPST[.3sA]
 ‘Debi is looking for the/an apple.’
 (elicitation PRAR 2010)
- b. *Debi seu kon-no.*
 Debi apple look.for-IND.NPST[.3sS]
 ‘Debi is looking for apples.’
 (elicitation PRAR 2010)

DOI in Chintang is formally more complex than DOM in Nepali. The reason for this is that it affects the verb and that verbs are grammatical hubs – they tend to be more closely intertwined with more other parts of a clause than arguments. As above for Nepali, the discussion here will focus on P even though P-AGR can also be governed by T and G and the term “object” will be used to refer to all relevant roles (i.e. all P-T-G which govern P-AGR). Also note that P is not as dominant in Chintang as it is in Nepali: out of 1912 objects annotated in Schikowski (2013), only 1202 (63%) were P.

It should be noted that the pattern found in Chintang is not object incorporation (as claimed for a parallel construction in Limbu, another Kiranti language, by Angdembe 1998). Ps which do not have AGR may be moved around freely (14), they may be omitted (15) (the verb *apt-* ‘shoot’ does license overt P and P agreement in other contexts), and they may form the head of a complex NP (16).

(14) Chintang (Kiranti, Tibeto-Burman)

Yum athaba kok=yaŋ car din kheŋa le?le ani
 salt or rice=also four day since only 1pi
ca-i-ki.

eat-1p[i]S-IND.NPST
 ‘Salt and rice we also only eat from four days after (the death of a close relative).’
 (CLC:LHLal.0715)

- (15) Chintang (Kiranti, Tibeto-Burman)
Ap-no=kha=lo!
 hit-IND.NPST[.3sS]=NMLZ=SURP
 ‘He shoots (at tangerines).’
 (CLC:CLLDCh1R06S01.342)

- (16) Chintang (Kiranti, Tibeto-Burman)
Aniŋ kaccakam-a num-no e
 how crude work-NTVZ do-IND.NPST[.3sS] PTCL
ba=go!
 PROX=NMLZ
 ‘What crude work this one does!’
 (CLC:CLLDCh1R02S04b.1685)

The pattern in question is also not an antipassive, since there is no dedicated marker such as a verbal affix indicating the constructional change and since P does not only remain a core argument but also gets the same case marking as in the default transitive construction.

2.2.2 Functional characteristics

The simplest approximation for the function of DOI in Chintang is specificity: specific Ps control agreement, non-specific Ps do not. Normal Ps usually correspond to an English NP with an article (*a* or *the*), whereas Ps without agreement normally correspond to an NP with zero article. Specificity comes in many flavours – see Enç (1991) and Farkas (2002) for overviews of the various distinctions that this label has been used for. The definition that captures best what happens in Chintang is as follows: a P is specific when a speaker is able to identify two or more instances of its referent with each other in discourse.

Note that this does not mean that the referent has to be topical or topicworthy. This is illustrated by the sentences in (17), which are some of the first sentences from a Chintang Pear Story (cf. Chafe 1980). The Pear Story movie starts by showing a green landscape with a tree and then a close-up of a pear. A man in the tree plucks two single pears. Even though these pears are mentioned in (17) for the first time and are completely unimportant for the rest of the story, both of them get P agreement (*puttoko*, *tisoko*) because they are well individuated and therefore easy to track.

- (17) Chintang (Kiranti, Tibeto-Burman)
- a. *Thitta siŋtaŋ the=kkha yuw-a-kt-e=ta*
 one tree big=NMLZbe.there-PST-IPFV-IND.PST[.3sS]=FOC
na, huŋ=go putt-o-ko.
 CTOP MED=NMLZ pluck-3[s]P-IND.NPST[.3sA]
 ‘There was a really big tree, and (now a man) plucks (one fruit).’
 (CLC:pear1-1.011)

- b. *Dhawa~dhawa pus-saŋa tis-o-ko,* *ar ko*
 hurry~INTENS pluck-CVB put.in-3[s]P-IND.NPST[.3sA] other
caĩ u-ta-no,
 PTCL 3[p]S-come-IND.NPST
copt-and-u-ku-ce=le,
 look.at-COMPL-3P-IND.NPST-[3sA.]3nsP=only
ba=go u-jhol-a-i? tis-o-ko.
 PROX=NMLZ 3sPOR-bag-NTVZ-LOC put.in-3[s]P-IND.NPST[.3sA]
 ‘Hurriedly he plucks and puts it in(to a bag), others come (into view), he only
 looks at them, this one he puts into his bag.’
 (CLC:pear 1-1.012)

- (18) Chintang (Kiranti, Tibeto-Burman)
Akka muda thap-ma-ʔã.
 1s stool fetch-1sS-IND.NPST
 ‘I’ll fetch a stool.’
 (field notes 2010)

Speaker-givenness of a referent is necessary but not sufficient for yielding P agreement. This is seen in example (19), where (19a) is a question and (19b) is the answer by another speaker. Here, the referent *kok* ‘rice’ has been mentioned before. However, because it is conceptualised as a mass and instances of masses cannot be easily identified with each other, it does not get P agreement even when it gets mentioned for the second time in (19b)⁴:

- (19) Chintang (Kiranti, Tibeto-Burman)

- a. *Ma, kok na huŋ=go-i?*
 Q rice CTOP MED=NMLZ-LOC
u-thuk-nik-niŋ=kha naŋ.
 3pS-cook-IND.NPST-NEG=NMLZ but
 ‘But they don’t cook rice there, do they?’
 (CLC:phidang talk.381)
- b. *Huŋ=go-i? u-thuk-no ni.*
 MED=NMLZ-LOC 3pS-cook-IND.NPST ASS
 ‘They cook (it) right there.’
 (CLC:phidang talk.383)

Masses can only be tracked – and hence trigger P agreement – when they are quantified. (20) shows an example for this: the referent *sa* ‘meat’ gets P agreement (*ucohatte*) because its quantification defines clear physical boundaries that make it possible to track it in discourse, which is a prerequisite for specificity:

⁴

Of course it is problematic to speak of referents here in the first place because saying that *the* referent has been mentioned twice seems to imply that identification across clauses is possible. “The referent” in this case is nothing more than a convenient abbreviation that really means ‘some parts of the mass’.

(20) Chintang (Kiranti, Tibeto-Burman)

Aseĩ *a-mma* *Kathmandukhad-a-loĩs-a*
last.time 1sPOR-mother Kathmandugo-PST-out-PST[.3sS]
belā=ta *a-nicha-ce-ŋa* *bisauli* *sa*
time=FOC 1sPOR-younger.sibling-ns-ERG 1.25kg meat
u-c-o-hatt-e!
3[p]A-eat-3[s]P-COMPL.TR-IND.PST

‘Last time my mother went to Kathmandu my brothers ate one and a half kilo of meat!’

(CLC:CLLDCh2R12S04.279)

Interestingly, individuals also usually get P agreement when they are quantified, as shown in (21), where both verbs (*utaduŋsuce*, *uhikkice*) have P agreement with *kharayoce* ‘hares’:

(21) Chintang (Kiranti, Tibeto-Burman)

Etti~ti=kha *kharayo-ce hicce*
this.big~INTENS=NMLZ hare-ns two
u-tad-u-ŋs-u-c-e *u-hik-ki-ce-ta.*
3[p]A-bring-3P-PRF-3P-ns-IND.PST 3[p]A-keep-IND.NPST-3nsP-CONT

‘He brought two hares as big as this and now he’s keeping them.’

(CLC:ctn talk01.039)

The reason for this seems to be that being able to quantify a referent mostly implies being able to pick out one group of referents and distinguish it from other groups. Of course this is not a strict entailment; when the referent is not fixed yet, even quantified Ps may stay without agreement:

(22) Chintang (Kiranti, Tibeto-Burman)

Akka sum-bhaŋ *ka-pha-pa* *maŋmi*
1s three-HUM.CLF ACT.PTCP-help-REF person
koĩ-yã-ŋã-ta, *jo=go* *nusayaŋ*
search-1sS-IND.NPST-CONT whoever=NMLZ CONCS
yaŋs-o.
be.good.for-[SBJV.3sA.]3[s]P

‘I’m searching for three helpers, anyone is okay.’

(elicitation RBK 2012)

A corpus study (Schikowski 2013) has revealed that quantifiability is not only an important prerequisite for specificity and implies specificity most of the time but can also serve as an annotation proxy for specificity. In an annotated subcorpus of the Chintang Language Corpus, where only quantifiability was annotated, 1198 of 1236 quantifiable object referents (97%) have agreement, and 369 of 388 non-quantifiable object referents (95%) do not have it.

Even though Chintang DOI is thus easy to explain based on functional factors in most cases, there are a couple of areas where it is semi-grammaticalised. We will briefly mention these to make the picture more complete. First, P agreement is very rare when P carries the number marker *-ce* [ns] as in (23):

- (23) Chintang (Kiranti, Tibeto-Burman)
Asinda akka paryatak maʔmi(-ce) khag-e-h-ẽ.*
 yesterday 1s tourist person-ns see-PST-1sS-IND.PST
 ‘Yesterday I saw (some) tourists.’
 (elicitation PRAR 2010)

Second, DOI interacts with parts of speech. It is completely impossible with SAP pronouns such as *akka* ‘I’, which form a morphosyntactically distinct class in Chintang:

- (24) Chintang (Kiranti, Tibeto-Burman)
 *Akka u-cop-no.
 1s 3[p]S-look.at-IND.NPST
 ‘They look at me.’
 (elicitation PRAR 2010)

An area where P agreement is much less frequent than one would expect by default are activities that contain a frequent object-predicate combination and that always follow the same scheme. This is illustrated in (25). Washing one’s knee is not a frequent or standardised activity, so *koŋci:k* ‘knee’ by default gets P agreement as in (25a). By contrast, hand-washing is something people do all the time and is much more routinised. Here, P agreement is more frequently absent than present (25b). Also note that the possessor may be expressed on *koŋci:k* but not on *muk* ‘hand’, even though it is clear from the context. P agreement and possession with *muk* are only found when there is a digression from the usual schema, as in (25c).

- (25) Chintang (Kiranti, Tibeto-Burman)
- a. *Rame-ŋa u-koŋci:k wachid-o-ko.*
 Ram-ERG 3sPOR-knee wash-3[s]P-IND.NPST[.3sA]
 ‘Rame washes his knee.’
 (elicitation PRAR 2010)
- b. *Rame muk wachi-no.*
 Ram hand wash-IND.NPST[.3sS]
 ‘Ram washes (his) hands.’
 (elicitation PRAR 2010)
- c. *Rame-ŋa thitta u-muk wachid-o-ko.*
 Ram-ERG one 3sPOR-hand wash-3[s]P-IND.NPST[.3sA]
 ‘Ram washes one of his hands.’
 (elicitation PRAR 2010)

Finally, P agreement is also very rare when the referent in P is something somebody says or thinks. This is well motivated because speakers usually do not utter or think predefined sentences. This kind of referents is thus similar to the cases mentioned above, where shortly before event time it is not clear yet which referent will be selected by an action. Accordingly, P agreement with verbs of saying and thinking is only possible in the rare case that their P gets reified, e.g. because it has been heard so often that it has acquired a distinct referential identity, as in (26b).

(26) Chintang (Kiranti, Tibeto-Burman)

- a. *Huŋ=go* *khali=ta* *namaste=mo* *cek-no.*
MED=NMLZ always=FOC namaste=CIT say-IND.NPST[.3sS]
'He always says "namaste."' (elicitation PRAR 2010)
- b. *Huĩ-sa-ŋa* *khali=ta* *namaste=mo* *cekt-o-ko.*
MED-OBL-ERG always=FOC namaste=CIT say-3[s]P-IND.NPST
'He always says his namaste.' (elicitation PRAR 2010)

2.3 Comparison of Nepali and Chintang

The short descriptions above have shown that DOM in Nepali and DOI in Chintang are different in many respects. We will focus on the functional differences here. For a more detailed comparison see Schikowski (2013:235).

Both patterns feature a binary, privative opposition. However, the marking systems into which these oppositions are embedded are rather different. The Nepali zero nominative alternates with a great variety of overt cases. By contrast, there are only two agreement patterns in Chintang (S agreement, A+P agreement). Thus, for Nepali it may be said that out of many possibilities two are chosen, whereas for Chintang the only two possibilities alternate. Trivial as this may sound, it means that the choice of case in Nepali may be said to be meaningful in a completely different way than the choice of agreement in Chintang. There is the question why out of all possible cases the dative alternates with the default case, whereas in Chintang, switching to S agreement is the only possible result of cancelling P agreement.

When it comes to the factors conditioning the two phenomena, the most remarkable difference is that the description of DOM in Nepali requires many factors whereas one (specificity) explains almost everything in Chintang. On a deeper level, many of the values that may trigger DOM in Nepali are unusual for P. For instance, most Ps in the NNC are not human or pronominal, so Ps that do have these properties are mostly marked by the dative. DOI in Chintang, by contrast, does not serve to mark unusual P – rather, it has the function of tracking P through discourse whenever they can be tracked. These differences are in accordance with more general tendencies of case marking and agreement: the most important function of case is to mark roles, whereas agreement serves to track referents.

3 DOM and DOI from a typological perspective

The description of Nepali DOM and Chintang DOI above has made it clear that these two phenomena may be very different when considered in two languages. In this section, we will provide a general overview of the makeup of DOM and DOI systems based on a cross-linguistic study of 178 languages (an extended version of the sample used in Iemmolo 2011).

For this study, each case of DOM or DOI was coded only with regard to the most relevant parameter (i.e. the parameter which takes priority over the others and has most explanatory power in that it renders DOM or DOI obligatory). This measure

is necessary in a typological study in order to make it possible to provide some generalisations on the main factors behind the phenomena under investigation. It is not meant to reduce the variety of factors influencing DOM and DOI in any individual language to a single factor.

In determining the dominant parameters for DOM and DOI, the indications given in the primary sources (grammars or specialised literature) were checked based on the examples or the texts provided by the grammarian. When the grammar was not explicit or by-passed the question of possible triggering parameters for the phenomena under investigation, the procedure adopted consisted in checking the connections between the distribution of the phenomenon and various semantic, pragmatic, and morpho-syntactic features. This procedure was particularly useful to assess the role of information-structural parameters in determining DOM and DOI: for example, as will be discussed below, when a grammar stated that the conditions for DOM and DOI to appear were related to “emphasis” or “pragmatic factors”, one of the interactions we looked for was the distribution of overt marking in morphosyntactic positions used to encode particular information-structural categories, such as dislocations and topicalisations.

The convenience sample utilised here comprises 127 languages showing DOM and 42 languages showing DOI. In addition, 6 languages have both DOM and DOI. Table 2 provides a summary of the distribution of DOM with respect to the most relevant parameter. Table 3 summarises the situation for DOI systems. In some cases, several parameters were judged to be equally relevant, which is why the rows do not sum up to 127 and 42, respectively.

Parameter	N	%
Animacy	45	34
Topicality	86	64
Dislocation	60	45
Definiteness	3	1

Table 2: Distribution of DOM systems relative to the main parameter

Parameter	N	%
Animacy	20	41
Topicality	28	58
Definiteness	1	2

Table 3: Distribution of DOI systems relative to the main parameter

In the following subsections we will present an overview of DOM and DOI systems based on animacy (Section 3.1), identifiability (Section 3.2), and topicality (Section 3.3). While topicality was not among the common factors introduced in Section 1.2 above, it will turn out to be of great importance for both DOM and DOI below. As we will see, DOM systems governed only by a single parameter are quite rare cross-linguistically. Rather, the coexistence of various factors as in Nepali (Section 2.1.2) is most common.

3.1 Animacy

In this section we will discuss DOM and DOI systems in which animacy synchronically takes priority over the other parameters. A first example is presented by the DOM system of Nepali discussed in Section 2.1.2 above. Animacy has been described as a central factor in most descriptions of Indo-Aryan DOI systems, and in the case of Nepali the corpus study in Schikowski (2013) could even show that the human/non-human distinction has the highest predictive power of all factors. It surpasses even specificity, which has sometimes been assumed to take precedence over animacy (Foster 1985) or to be on a par with it (Abadie 1974; Li 2007a).

Another example of a DOM system where animacy takes priority over the other parameters is Maltese (Afro-Asiatic > Semitic, Malta). Pronouns and proper names trigger the obligatory use of the preposition *(li)l*, as in (27a). Nouns lower in the animacy hierarchy, such as human common nouns and non-human nouns may be optionally overtly coded as in (27c), while DOM is blocked with inanimate Ps, no matter whether they are definite or not, as in (27d).

(27) Maltese (Semitic)

- a. *It-tabib bagħat lil-u.*
 DEF-doctor send.PST.3SG.M OBJ-3SG.M
 ‘It was him the doctor sent’
 (Borg and Mifsud 2002:35)
- b. *Tereza rat lit-tifel /it-tifel.*
 Therese see.PST.3SG.F OBJ.DEF-boy /DEF-boy
 ‘Therese saw the boy’
 (Borg and Mifsud 2002:35)
- c. *It-tabib bagħat lil wieħed ragel b-ir-risposta.*
 DEF-doctor send.PST.3SG.M OBJ one man with-DEF-answer
 ‘The doctor sent a certain man with the message’
 (Borg and Mifsud 2002:35)
- d. *Marija qabdet il-ballun.*
 Mary catch.PST.3SG.F DEF-ball
 ‘Mary caught the ball’
 (Borg and Mifsud 2002:35)

As can be seen from example (27b), the presence of formal de finiteness (indicated by the definite determiner) along with animacy is not a necessary and sufficient condition for DOM to appear. However, specificity seems to be relevant with indefinite Ps, since indefinite specific Ps may receive DOM, as opposed to non-specific ones, as shown by example (27c) above. Thus, although in Maltese DOM is primarily regulated by animacy, we can also observe that animacy alone would not suffice to explain the distribution of the marker, which is governed by the identifiability of the P as well. In fact, the marker is obligatory with NP categories which are human and by default uniquely identifiable, such as pronouns and proper names. With other kinds of NPs, beside the animacy condition, the distribution of DOM is conditioned by its

identifiability status. That is, only animate Ps can be coded: the actual occurrence of overt marking then depends on whether the referent of P is identifiable or not.

Similar systems, in which specificity distinctions come into play, are fairly common in animacy-based DOM. Palauan represents an interesting case in point. Both DOM and DOI are obligatorily used to encode human Ps, but with a peculiar complementary distribution. When human Ps are governed by an imperfective predicate, they trigger DOM via the preposition *er* (Josephs 1975), as shown by the examples in (28):

(28) Palauan (Austronesian)

- a. *Ng omeka er a ngalek a sechelik.*
 3SG eat.IPFV OBJ DET child DET friend
 ‘My friend is feeding a child’
 (Nuger 2007:5)
- b. *A sensei a-mengelebed er a re-ngalek.*
 DET teacher R-hit OBJ DET PL-child
 ‘The teacher is hitting the children’
 (Woolford 2000:219)
- c. *A sensei a omes er a re-ngalek.*
 DET teacher TOP see.IPFV OBJ DET PL-child
 ‘The teacher is looking at the children’
 (Nuger 2007:5)

When the governing predicate is in the perfective aspect, human Ps trigger DOI on the verb (Josephs 1975; Nuger 2007; Woolford 2000), as shown by the examples in (29):

(29) Palauan (Austronesian)

- a. *Mchelebed-ii a ngalek.*
 hit-PFV.3SG DET child
 ‘Hit the child’
 (Josephs 1975:375)
- b. *Ak mils-a a Droteo er a party.*
 I see-PFV.3SG DET Droteo at DET party
 ‘I saw Droteo at a party’
 (Josephs 1975:324)
- c. *Ak mils-terir a retede el sensei.*
 I see-PFV.3PL DET three LNK teachers
 ‘I saw three teachers’
 (Josephs 1975:43)

Basically human Ps always trigger the use of either DOM or DOI, which are in complementary distribution, since DOI is only used in conjunction with the perfective aspect whereas DOM is only found with the imperfective aspect. However, many examples are found in which DOM or DOI encode inanimate Ps, provided that they

are *singular* and *specific*, as shown by the examples in (30). Thus, specificity and number are also relevant parameters for DOM and DOI. However, they do not render the appearance of these constructions obligatory, as opposed to humanness.

(30) Palauan (Austronesian)

- a. *Ng menga er a mera a sechelik.*
 3SG eat.IPFV OBJ DET orange DET friend
 ‘My friend is eating a (particular) orange/the orange’
 (Nuger 2009:139)
- b. *Ng mo kol-ii a meradel a sechelik.*
 3SG go eat-PFV.3SG DET orange DET friend
 ‘My friend is going to eat an orange/the orange’
 (Nuger 2009:139)

Animacy-based DOI systems seems to be somewhat stricter with respect to the interplay of parameters. For example, in Tauya (Papua New Guinea, Trans-New-Guinean), DOI is restricted to animate Ps, with other parameters playing no role at all. This is illustrated by the examples in (31), where there is DOI in (31a) with the animate P, while DOI is absent when the P is inanimate (31b):

(31) Tauya (Trans-New-Guinean)

- a. *ʔumu-nen-fe-i-ʔa.*
 die-3PL.OBJ-TR-IND
 ‘They killed them’
 (MacDonald 1990:105)
- b. *Fanu-ra amufo ni-a-ʔa.*
 man-TOP big eat-3SG-IND
 ‘The man ate the big one’
 (MacDonald 1990:105)

3.2 Identifiability

In this section we will look at systems primarily based on identifiability, i.e. on definiteness and/or specificity. Note that we do not restrict ourselves to formal definiteness (expressed, for instance, by the presence of overt definite determiners).

As a matter of fact, formal definiteness is dominant only in a handful of cases, where the presence of, for instance, an overt determiner makes DOM or DOI obligatory. Modern Hebrew (Afro-Asiatic > Semitic, Israel) is one such case, where the DOM preposition *’et* is not only obligatory with personal pronouns and proper names but also whenever P is accompanied by a determiner or a possessive, as shown by the opposition between (32a) and (32b):

(32) Modern Hebrew (Semitic)

- a. *Baláti et ha-zvuv.*
 swallow:PST.1SG OBJ DEF-fly

'I swallowed the fly.'
(Glinert 1989:157)

- b. *Baláti* *zvuv.*
swallow:PST.1SG fly
'I swallowed a fly.'
(Glinert 1989:157)

Similarly, in Hungarian (Uralic > Ugric, Hungary), DOI is present when the verb governs a third person pronoun (overt or null) (33a), a proper name (33b), a noun accompanied by a definite determiner (33c) or by a possessive suffix (33d), or a direct object clause (Rounds 2009; Coppock and Wechsler 2012:16-18).

(33) Hungarian (Ugric)

- a. *Lát-om.*
see-1SG.OBJ
'I see him/it.'
(Rounds 2009:17)
- b. *Lát-om* *Zsuzsá-t.*
see-1SG.OBJ Zsuzsa-ACC
'I see Zsuzsa.'
(Rounds 2009:17)
- c. *Eltitkol-om* *valamennyi* *találkozás-t.*
keep.secret-1SG.OBJ each meeting-ACC
'I keep each meeting secret.'
(Coppock and Wechsler 2012:703)
- d. *Olvás-om* *Péter vers-é-t.*
read-1SG.OBJ Peter poem-3SG.POR-ACC
'I am reading Peter's poem.'
(Coppock and Wechsler 2012:704)

DOI in Hungarian is triggered by the formal definiteness of the P, as has been repeatedly observed in the literature (Moravcsik 1974; Lazard 2001; Kiss 2011; Coppock and Wechsler 2012; among others). DOI is absent (i.e. the so-called subjective conjugation is used) when the P is unspecified for definiteness or is a first/second person pronoun.

It is also possible to find the opposite pattern of this, where the presence of overt definiteness marking blocks the appearance of DOM. Only two languages have been found to display this behaviour, viz. Zuni (isolate, New Mexico) and Corsican (Indo-European > Romance, Corsica). In both languages, Ps which would be likely to receive overt marking, such as human Ps, must be unmarked when modified by a determiner, a quantifier, or a numeral. The following examples from Corsican illustrate this complementary distribution: the proper noun as well as the pronoun in (34a) receive accusative marking, which is banned with the definite human P, as shown by (34b):

(34) Zuni (isolate)

- a. *Vegu chè tù preferisci più à Penelope chè*
see.PRS.1SG that you prefer.2SG.PRS more ACC Penelope that
à mè.
ACC me
'I see that you prefer more Penelope than me.'
(Neuburger and Stark 2014:366)
- b. *Tutti quant'è no' simu salutemu l'omu d'azione*
all together we be.1PL.PRS greet.1PL.PRS DEF.man of.action
e u babbu di a Négritude.
and DEF father of DEF Négritude
'We all together greet the man of the action and the father of the Négritude.'
(Neuburger and Stark 2014:378)

Neuburger and Stark (2014) argue that the motivation for the incompatibility of the formal expression of definiteness and the differential object marker in Corsican lies in the fact that the object marker is a morphosyntactic means for the encoding of definiteness on a par with determiners, quantifiers, and numerals and can therefore not be combined with such markers. The situation in Zuni (Nichols 1997) is similar. One might hypothesise that accusative marking came to be in complementary distribution with de finiteness marking in these languages because over the course of time accusative marking became itself a marker of de finiteness, due to the fact that accusative case was most commonly found with definite Ps.

A typical example for this is presented by the DOM system of Turkish (Altaic > Turkic, Turkey). Accusative marking in (35a) triggers a definite interpretation, while in (35b) it indicates that the referent, although indefinite, is specific (i.e. both the speaker and the hearer have a mental representation of it). When the P referent is unidentifiable, as in (35c), no marking is present:

(35) Turkish (Turkic)

- a. *(Ben) kitab-ı oku-du-m.*
1SG book-ACC read-PST-1SG
'I read the book.'
(von Heusinger and Kornfilt 2005:8)
- b. *(Ben) bir kitab-ı oku-du-m.*
1SG a book-ACC read-PST-1SG
'I read a certain book.'
(von Heusinger and Kornfilt 2005:8)
- c. *(Ben) bir kitap oku-du-m.*
1SG a book read-PST-1SG
'I read a book'
(von Heusinger and Kornfilt 2005:8)

With regard to DOI, one case in question is the alternation found in Chintang, described in Section 2.2.2 above, where specificity (closely linked to quantifiability)

is the only factor governing agreement with P and other object-like roles. However, in many DOI systems identity plays a more intricate role. For instance, in Swahili (Niger-Congo > Bantu, Tanzania) DOI is nearly obligatory with animate Ps (36a) (including the question word ‘who’), while it is optional with inanimate Ps, as in (36b,c) (Wald 1979, 1997; Seidl and Dimitriadis 1997; Marten and Kula ms). When DOI is used with an inanimate direct object, the P must be interpreted as definite:

(36) Swahili (Bantu)

- a. *ni-li-*(mw)-on-a* *Juma.*
 SUBJ.1SG-PST-OBJ-see-FV Juma
 ‘I saw Juma.’
 (Marten and Kula ms:5)
- b. *ni-li-ki-on-a* *kitabu.*
 SUBJ.1SG-PST-OBJ-see-FV book
 ‘I saw the book.’
 (Marten and Kula ms:5)
- c. *ni-li-on-a* *kitabu.*
 SUBJ.1SG-PST-see-FV book
 ‘I read a book’
 (Marten and Kula ms:5)

In many cases, definiteness and specificity alone do not satisfactorily account for the appearance of DOM and DOI. As will be argued in the following section, many of these can be explained by taking into account information structure.

3.3 Topicality

Topicality is another important factor for DOM and DOI, as has already been demonstrated by the example of Nepali (Section 2.1.2), where mental presence (in most cases approximatable via discourse frequency) can explain many instances of the dative where animacy and specificity alone would fail.

Traditionally, however, topicality is not among the factors which have been considered to be most highly relevant for DOM and DOI. As a consequence, most descriptive work has not devoted a lot of attention to this factor. In order to nevertheless get an impression of its relevance, formal indicators had to be checked. In particular, we examined the occurrence of DOM and DOI with:

1. syntactic topicalisation, dislocation, and focalisation environments;
2. prototypical focus elements, such as *wh*-elements.

Particularly relevant for DOM is the interaction with syntactic topicalisation or dislocation. In 60 languages in the sample (i.e. 45%), DOM is either restricted to or becomes obligatory with topicalised or dislocated Ps. For example, in Mangghuer (Altaic > Mongolic, China; word order SOV), DOM is used with definite and indefinite specific Ps, as exemplified by (37a) and (37b):

(37) Mangghuer (Mongolic)

- a. *Gan mori wuni-jiang.*
 3SG horse ride-OBJ.PFV
 ‘S/he rode a horse.’
 (Slater 2003:165)
- b. *Gan mori-ni wuni-jiang.*
 3SG horse-OBJ ride-OBJ.PFV
 ‘S/he rode the horse.’
 (Slater 2003:165)

As is clear from the examples above, when the standard word order is followed, the presence of overt marking depends upon the identifiability of the P referent. However, DOM becomes obligatory when P is moved to the sentence-initial position, which is restricted to topical constituents (Slater 2003:189):

(38) Mangghuer (Mongolic)

- a. *Dimei-ni bi he-ji xi-a bai.*
 bread-OBJ 1SG take-IPFV go-VOLUNT EMPH
 ‘The bread, let me take (it).’
 (Slater 2003:124)
- b. *Gaga-ni gan-si lake gher-gha-jiang.*
 elder_brother-OBJ 3-PL pull go.out-CAUS-OBJ.PFV
 ‘Elder Brother, they dragged out.’
 (Slater 2003:124)

A similar constraint is at work in the Muskogean language Chocktaw (Broadwell 2006). According to (Broadwell 2006), DOM is “optional” in every context when the standard word order (SOV) is followed. However, it becomes mandatory when the object is topicalised by moving it to the sentence-initial position, as is illustrated by the opposition between (39a) and (39b). As Broadwell himself acknowledges, speakers “interpret NPs with overt accusative marking as topical” (Broadwell 2006:74) and as the current centre of attention:

(39) Chocktaw (Muskogean)

- a. *John-at takkon-(a) chop-a-h.*
 John-NOM peach-OBJ buy-TNS
 ‘John bought a peach.’
 (Broadwell 2006:32)
- b. *Takkon-*(a) John-at chop-a-h.*
 peach-OBJ John-NOM buy-TNS
 ‘John bought a peach.’
 (Broadwell 2006:39)

It is important to note the presence of obligatory overt A marking in both examples, which makes it unlikely that the use of DOM with topicalised Ps should be due to ambiguity avoidance.

Topicality is relevant for DOI as well. As in the case of DOM, in many languages only topical Ps can be indexed on the verb. A clear example of a topicality-based DOI system comes from Chichêwa (Niger-Congo > Bantu, Malawi and elsewhere). Chichêwa shows both A and P indexation in its verbal morphology. In finite verb forms S/A indexation is obligatory, while DOI can be employed only when the P is topical (Bresnan and Mchombo 1987:746). Bresnan and Mchombo suggest this based on word order evidence. As a matter of fact, when there is no DOI, P must obligatorily follow the verb and cannot be freely moved, as shown by (40a) as opposed to (40b). By contrast, when there is DOI, the P appears in dislocated position as in (40c,d) and all word order permutations are possible:

(40) Chichêwa (Bantu)

- a. *Njûchi* *zi-ná-lúm-a* *alenje.*
 bee.PL SUBJ-PST-bite-IND hunter.PL
 ‘The bees bit the hunters.’
 (Bresnan and Mchombo 1987:744)
- b. **Alenje* *zi-ná-lúm-a* *njûch.*
 hunter.PL SUBJ-PST-bite-IND bee.PL
 ‘The bees bit the hunters.’
 (Bresnan and Mchombo 1987:745)
- c. *Njûchi* *zi-ná-wá-lúm-a* *alenje.*
 bee.PL SUBJ-PST-OBJ-bite-IND hunter.PL
 ‘The bees bit them, the hunters.’
 (Bresnan and Mchombo 1987:745)
- d. *Alenje* *njûchi* *zi-ná-wá-lúm-a.*
 hunter.PL bee.PL SUBJ-PST-OBJ-bite-IND
 ‘The bees bit them, the hunters.’
 (Bresnan and Mchombo 1987:745)

Bresnan and Mchombo (1987) observe that DOI is prohibited to co-occur with Ps that are not topical, expressed by a *wh*-phrase, a cognate object, or part of an idiom or a light verb construction, and in general with argument-focus Ps (Bresnan and Mchombo 1987:759–764). Examples (41a) and (41b) illustrate the impossibility for DOI to index a *wh*-element (motivated by the fact that these elements are prototypically focal):

(41) Chichêwa (Bantu)

- a. *Kodí mu-ku-fún-á* *chyiâni?*
 Q 2SG-PRS-want-IND what
 ‘What do you want?’
 (Bresnan and Mchombo 1987:759)

- b. ??*Kodí mu-ku-chí-fún-á chyîâni?*
 Q 2SG-PRS-OBJ(7)want-IND what(7)
 ‘What do you want?’
 (Bresnan and Mchombo 1987:760)

Other facts that support the close link between topicality and the presence of DOM and DOI come from the interaction of marked Ps with negation. Ps that trigger DOI remain outside the scope of negation, which is a typical feature of topical constituents. As is well known, topical elements must be presupposed, and therefore referents of topical expression are presupposed to exist (Lambrecht 1994:154). This is illustrated by Babine-Witsuwit’en (Na-Dene, USA): whenever there is DOI, the P has to be outside the scope of negation. Thus, in example (42), the indexed P ‘car’ is unaffected by the negation:

- (42) Babine-Witsuwit’en (Na-Dene)
Lillian George bi-ka’ we-yu-taskitl
 Lillian George 3SG-car NEG-3SG.OBJ.buy
 ‘Lillian isn’t going to buy George’s car’
 (Gunlogson 2001)

A similar situation is found in DOM systems. Overtly coded Ps are often outside the scope of negation, as exemplified by (43) from Kannada (Dravidian, India). In (43a), the P can be interpreted either as inside or outside the scope of negation. The presence of DOM in (43b) makes it impossible for the P to be interpreted within the scope of negation:

- (43) Kannada (Dravidian)
- a. *Naanu pustaka ood-al-illa.*
 1SG.NOM book read-INF-NEG
 ‘I didn’t read any/a book.’
 (Lidz 2006:12)
- b. *Naanu pustaka-vannu ood-al-illa.*
 1SG.NOM book-OBJ read-INF-NEG
 ‘I didn’t read a book.’
 (Lidz 2006:12)

Additional evidence for the relevance of topicality comes from differences in intonation related to the presence vs. absence of DOM. For instance, in Eastern Armenian, when a P receives DOM, the main stress is assigned to the verb only, and the P must be interpreted as definite, as in (44a). Unmarked Ps instead systematically attract stress:

- (44) Eastern Armenian
- a. *Ara-n girk-ə AYR-ETS.*
 Ara-NOM book-OBJ burn-AOR.3SG
 ‘Ara BURNT the book.’

- b. *Ara-n GIRK gn-ets.*
Ara-NOM book buy-AOR.3SG
'Ara bought a BOOK/BOOKS.'
(Megerdooonian 1999:313-314)

When the P forms part of the focal domain, it does not receive DOM, and is therefore stressed. By contrast, when the P is outside the focus domain, only the verb is stressed, whereas the marked P is de-stressed because of its presupposed, topical nature. This pattern is a further manifestation of the link between topicality and DOM.

A topic that needs to be addressed at this point concerns the link between DOM, DOI, identifiability, and information structure. We have seen in Section 3.2 that definiteness and specificity in their pragmatic sense often interact with DOM and DOI in that these constructions will be preferentially used with definite and/or specific Ps. We have also observed that in systems where the topical status of the P triggers the presence of DOM or DOI, the referent of the P must be definite or receives a definite interpretation, as in the Eastern Armenian or Mangghuer examples discussed above.

This fact is not unexpected, given that topical constituents tend to be occupied by definite and specific referents (Chafe 1976, 1987; Lambrecht 1994; Leonetti 2008). As a matter of fact, indefinite non-specific entities are generally not allowed in topic position, because they cannot serve as topics (Givón 2001:265): indefinite NPs used in topical positions receive a specific, or at least generic, interpretation which is forced exactly by their being topical (see Erteschik-Shir 1997; Portner and Yabushita 2001; Endriss 2009).

4 Conclusions

4.1 Explanations for DOM and DOI

As mentioned in Section 1.3, two main explanations have been proposed for DOM (mostly implicitly including DOI), namely the distinguishing and the indexing or high-lighting explanations. Under the distinguishing analysis, which traditionally covers only case marking, DOM and DOI serve to correctly allocate the roles of A and P when they share identical semantic properties, like animacy or definiteness. By contrast, in the indexing or highlighting view, DOM and DOI serve to highlight salient semantic and pragmatic properties of the referents of arguments, like animacy, definiteness, the degree of affectedness, or the secondary topic status of the P. Thus, the highlighting approach calls for a paradigmatic differentiation among Ps based on their semantic properties, as opposed to the distinguishing approach, which takes DOM as indicating a syntagmatic opposition between Ps and As.

The discussion above has made it clear that both approaches are not sufficient to explain the actual data. Disambiguation between A and P as a factor behind DOM and DOI is very weakly represented in the languages of the world, completely absent from Chintang and hard to distinguish from topicality in Nepali. Apart from its use for describing individual systems, it is also not suitable as a theoretical motivation for differential object coding. The reason is that differential object coding also occurs in languages where there is no need for disambiguation because of dedicated formal markers (e.g. an ergative to mark A). Further, if disambiguation was the driving factor behind DOM and DOI, we would expect differential coding in both directions because

it should be equally feasible to mark A or P distinctly. Most importantly, though, DOM and DOI in general do not seem to depend on the relation between A and P but are in the majority of cases determined by properties of P only. If disambiguation was central for these phenomena, one would expect it to be more frequent where the relation between A and P is not sufficiently clear – for instance, where both A and P are inanimate (‘the rock smashed the house’) or with symmetric scenarios where action in both directions is possible (‘the cat saw the dog’).

The indexing approach is somewhat closer to our view. The crucial point of divergence here concerns the motivations behind highlighting certain Ps. Why are “high” P highlighted while A and other arguments are not? And why is it necessary to mark different kinds of P differently instead of using one case marker across the board? We believe that these are important questions that should be considered by any theory of differential coding.

4.2 Differential object coding as motivated by discourse

The analysis of DOM and DOI systems in the languages in our sample, as well as in additional languages outside the sample (e.g. Romance languages, see Iemmolo 2010, 2011), suggests that the link between DOM/DOI and the semantic and information structural properties we have discussed so far is motivated by the functions these constructions perform in discourse.

On the one hand, discourse functions are directly relevant in many systems. One example is Nepali DOM, but many others have been briefly mentioned above. In languages where topicality is not the dominant parameter, it is nonetheless often found as a secondary parameter besides other factors, such as definiteness and animacy. Most importantly, discourse can serve as a theoretical bridge between topicality and such factors.

Definiteness is related to discourse in that most topical referents are definite and vice versa. That is, the marking of definite referents can be viewed as an extension of the marking of topical referents. The same may be said about animacy. Many DOM and DOI systems that are synchronically based on animacy are the result of the grammaticalisation of earlier topicality-based systems (see Iemmolo 2011). Since human referents are the most topical, over time this can lead to the conventionalisation of DOM and DOI to human Ps, irrespective of their information status. This development is an instance of a more general pattern of grammaticalisation whereby a function that is highly frequent with some pattern (e.g., definiteness/animacy with DOM/DOI) is reanalysed as primary, whereas another function (topicality) gets blurred and may finally lose its relevance (cf. Bybee 2010). Also note that DOM systems frequently originate from the grammaticalisation of topic constructions, as shown in Iemmolo (2011).

To summarise, contrary to what has been assumed in the literature, DOM and DOI systems do not primarily arise from the need to distinguish between the two arguments of a transitive clause or to indicate a high degree of animacy or affectedness of the P referent per se. Rather, they reflect the special status of certain Ps in discourse.

The central role of discourse also implies that DOM and DOI are never optional. Rather, where DOM and DOI are obligatory with some referents (usually those higher on the animacy/definiteness hierarchies) and “optional” with less animate/definite referents, topicality may be the determining factor in the seemingly optional cases.

This does, of course, not exclude more complex variable systems such as the one we observed in Nepali.

4.3 Differences between DOM and DOI

Above we have seen that both DOM and DOI are grounded in discourse. However, a more careful analysis of their functions reveals that they play different roles in this domain.

DOM in general seems to be associated with Ps featuring properties which are not expected in this role because they are rarely associated with it in discourse, as has been argued in detail in Iemmolo 2011 and Schikowski 2013. Examples for such unexpected properties are animacy, definiteness, and topicality – Ps tend to be inanimate, indefinite, and non-topical (*contra*, e.g. Dalrymple and Nikolaeva 2011). This is confirmed by several corpus studies. For instance, in the corpus of Nepali analysed in this study, where animacy is an important variable for the appearance of DOM, only 9% of Ps are human, and only 3% are other animate beings. Likewise, low percentages are also found for variables such as givenness and identifiability. The tendency for Ps to be inanimate, indefinite, and new has also been documented for many other languages (see, e.g. the papers in Dubois and Ashby 2003), such as Spanish, Roviana, French, and Korean.

This rarity leads to the unexpectedness of animate, definite, topical Ps in discourse. The propensity of languages to mark Ps with unexpected properties derives from the importance of predictability (Hume 2004; Bornkessel-Schlesewsky and Schlewsky 2009:91), which requires that grammatical relations in a clause be assigned in accordance with the expectations of the language user, built up through frequency. Thus, frequency effects themselves can account for what has been referred to as markedness effects in DOM systems so far (Bybee 2001, 2010). This analysis differs from the distinguishing approach in that only properties of P and not the similarity between A and P are viewed as relevant for DOM. It also differs from the indexing group of approaches in clearly stating the connection between the role of P and the factors behind marking it differentially as well as in not requiring inherent saliency.

It should be stressed that unexpectedness is not an absolute property of topical or topic-worthy Ps. On the one hand, such Ps are unexpected because of the low frequency of their semantic or information-structural features. On the other hand, we observe that not all Ps showing these properties receive overt marking. This derives from the crucial role that the discourse context plays in determining the presence vs. absence of DOM in that it is up to the speaker to construe a given referent in P position as “important” enough to be overtly marked, which motivates the apparent optionality often reported for DOM (and DOI).

Let us now contrast DOM with DOI. Most of the literature on differential object coding has either concentrated on DOM alone or has implicitly or explicitly extended the accounts proposed for DOM to DOI as well, as e.g. in Croft (1988) or Dalrymple and Nikolaeva (2011). However, apart from the trivial formal differences between DOM and DOI that are related to their representing head-marking and dependent-marking, respectively (cf. Nichols 1986), they are also different on the functional level and may emerge from different diachronic processes.

A first hint to this is the fact that they need not depend on each other (contrary to what is assumed by many scholars, see e.g. Baker 1996). An example of a system where DOM and DOI occur independently is Amharic (Afro-Asiatic > Semitic,

Ethiopia). Here, DOM is obligatory with definite and dislocated Ps, while DOI is used to encode the continuity of the P referent (Amberber 2005):

(45) Amharic (Semitic)

- a. *Lamma wiffaw-in j-aj-al.*
Lemma dog-DEF-ACC 3M.SG-see-AUX
'Lemma sees the dog.'
(Baker 2012:257)
- b. *Lamma wiffa-w-in j-aj-aw-al.*
Lemma dog-DEF-ACC 3M.SG-see-3SG.M.OBJ-AUX
'Lemma sees the dog.'
(Baker 2012:257)

That DOM and DOI may be conditioned by very different variables has also been shown above by the contrastive study of Nepali and Chintang. Notwithstanding a couple of peculiarities, the pattern that emerged there corresponds to the pattern found on the typological level: DOM is a special type of case marking and therefore intimately linked to properties of the role P – in particular, DOM is associated with Ps with properties that are unexpected because of their low relative frequency in all Ps. By contrast, DOI is a special type of agreement and is therefore primarily concerned with reference tracking. Thus, one may say that while DOI is associated with continuity (one referent is specific or topical enough to be tracked), DOM is associated with a discontinuity (of the kind that arises when a high referent occupies P). This also explains why DOM is cross-linguistically so often used for shifting or contrasting topics, which does not usually happen with DOI.

That the two strategies carry out different functions is also corroborated by the different construction types with which they are associated. DOM occurs very frequently in conjunction with topicalisations and dislocations, or with positions reserved to topical referents (see Iemmolo 2011 ch. 6–7 for further discussion). DOI is instead associated with highly accessible referents, which are normally referred to by zero anaphora and analogous continuity markers (Givón 1983; Iemmolo 2011).

Furthermore, DOM systems often require a multifactorial analysis, as illustrated by the example of Nepali, whereas DOI systems seem to be simpler, as in the example of Chintang, which is extreme, given that here a single factor dominates. This difference also matches the different macro-functions of DOM and DOI: referents have a plethora of properties that may serve as the basis for unexpectedness, whereas the trackability of referents depends on their accessibility.

Nepali DOM also conforms to the cross-linguistic generalisation that overt object marking is the restricted and less frequent coding means as compared to zero marking. This is also what is generally found in DOI. Chintang, where P agreement is the default, is a notable exception to this tendency and patterns with typical antipassives in this respect.

Abbreviations

- 1 1st person
2 2nd person

3	3rd person
A	agent
ACC	accusative
ACT	active
AOR	aorist
ASS	assertive
AUX	auxiliary
CAUS	causative
CIT	citation particle
CLF	classifier
COMPL	completive
COMP	comparative
CONCS	concessive
Cont	continuous
CTOP	contrastive topic
CVB	converb
DAT	dative
DEF	definite
DET	determiner
DIST	distal deixis
EMPH	emphatic
EQU	equative
ERG	ergative
FOC	focus
f/F	feminine
GEN	genitive
HH	high-honorific
HUM	human
i	inclusive
IND	indicative
INF	infinitive
INTENS	intensification
IPFV	imperfective
LNK	linker
LOC	locative
M	masculine
MED	medial deixis
MH	mid-honorific
NEG	negation
NMLZ	nominalizer
NOM	nominative
NPST	nonpast
ns	non-singular
NTVZ	nativiser
OBJ	object
OBL	oblique case
p	plural
P	patient
PASS	passive
PFV	perfective

PL	plural
POR	possessor
PRF	perfect
PROG	progressive
PROX	proximal deixis
PRS	present
PST	past
PTCL	particle
PTCP	participle
Q	question particle
REFL	reflexive
REF	referential

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